

Regulating Vehicle Access
for improved Livability

Deliverable 2.7

UVAR Innovation Observatory Report

Future options

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Summary sheet

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Abstract	The aim of this deliverable is to review new mobility products and services of direct relevance for the development of existing UVARs and for the execution of new UVARs. This deliverable is designed to deliver an update on the current state of affairs in the development, diffusion and market penetration of different technologies adopted to organise, implement and manage UVARs.
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About ReVeAL

ReVeAL – Regulating Vehicle Access for Improved Liveability – is a CIVITAS project funded by the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme. The goal of ReVeAL is to add Urban Vehicle Access Regulations (UVAR) to the standard range of urban mobility transition approaches of cities across Europe. The overarching mission of the project is to enable cities to optimise urban space and transport network usage through new and integrated packages of urban vehicle access policies and technologies. Such policies can lead to fewer emissions, less noise and improved accessibility and quality of life, which especially benefits the people living in these cities. These policies can also encourage more sustainable transport choices, enabling cities to become more liveable, ultimately healthier and more attractive for every member of society. To this end, ReVeAL combines conceptual work and case study research with hands-on UVAR implementation in six pilot cities, as well as systematic stakeholder interaction through professional communication activities.

Different UVAR measures have been developed, implemented and tested in the cities of Helmond (NL), Jerusalem (IL), London (UK), Padova (IT), Vitoria-Gasteiz (ES) and the project leader Bielefeld (DE). Apart from these cities, the project partners are Ghent University (BE), Università di Padova (IT), POLIS (BE), Rupprecht Consult (DE), Sadler Consultants (DE), Transport for London (UK), TRT (IT), V-Tron (NL) and WSP Sweden (SE). The project started in June 2019 and runs for 42 months.

ReVeAL looks at a range of UVAR measures, both established and cutting-edge approaches, grouped under the three Measure Fields: 1. Regulatory Measures (areas that are regulated by rules, e.g. where only vehicles emitting zero emissions, or low emission are permitted or a traffic limited zone). 2. Spatial interventions (access regulations based on area planning and design, and physical interventions in the public realm) and 3. Pricing aspects (financial charging for accessing specific areas).

Introduction

The aim of this deliverable is to review new mobility products and services of direct relevance for the improvement of existing Urban Vehicle Access Regulation¹ (UVARs), and for the execution of new UVARs. The scope of this deliverable is focused specifically on new mobility products and services deemed to have tangible potential to significantly facilitate, influence, enhance, or in other ways, directly contribute to the development of existing, or execution of new, UVARs. For this deliverable, we use the term “technologies” to refer to technologies which have been adapted for use in the realm of mobility and transport systems, and as such, constitute *mobility products and services*. This deliverable is designed to provide an update on the current state of affairs in the development, diffusion and market penetration of different technologies adopted to organise, implement and manage UVARs.

We build upon the findings from Milestones 10 and 11 from the ReVeAL project in the design of this deliverable. These milestones comprise an account of a consultation with relevant actors (Milestone 10) and an inventory and assessment of the resilience of the different building blocks employed to execute UVARs in different contexts (Milestone 11). Milestone 10 provided an inventory of UVAR-relevant technology developments; assessed the maturity of the respective technologies; identified the challenges suppliers and cities face; and assessed when said challenges are expected to be overcome. The initial intention of the current report (Deliverable 2.7) was to trace the developments that have taken place since Milestone 10 was published. However, even if the rate of change is fast, huge changes have not taken place in this short timeframe. Some incremental changes are likely to have taken place at business level for some individual actors. While it is unlikely that there would be considerable willingness to disclose such developments, we can draw on some lessons learned in the different contexts, where, for instance, the development of some UVARs is now seen as redundant due to the diffusion of other technologies, e.g., electric vehicles.

With this report, we give an overview of how different types of technologies have been implemented for existing UVARs in different contexts. We then **give an insight into the scope for the potential development of said technologies in existing and new UVARs**. This is to give **a perspective on how the future of UVAR might look**.

We then examine how policies shape the development and execution of UVARs, and how business models can be developed in tandem with these policies. The future of UVAR implementation is deemed to be rather dependent on the political and financial circumstances in the various contexts. The perspective presented is pervaded by these premises. Potential impacts on transport systems and society more broadly are then discussed.

¹ See the ReVeAL glossary for further information: [Glossary » Civitas ReVeAL \(civitas-reveal.eu\)](#)

Methods

For this deliverable, we identified which technologies, adapted as mobility products and services, are of key importance for the development of existing UVARs and the execution of new UVARs, now and into the near future. In some instances, we examined and detailed the ways in which different types of technologies have been employed in the different types of measures involved in the execution of UVARs. Furthermore, we examined the palpable market penetration² of the respective technologies. We then considered the conditions that need to be in place for a more expansive market penetration of these technologies and their corresponding application in UVAR execution.

In order to gain a state-of-the-art account of the status of UVARs and their related technologies, a combination of search approaches was employed. This involved:

1. Building on the findings from Milestones 10 and 11 and Deliverables 3.1 and 5.2 from the ReVeAL project³ and using these findings as leads in the resumed search.
2. Drawing on findings from relevant EU projects dealing with UVAR-related issues.
3. Drawing on experience from relevant actors, including partners in the ReVeAL project.
4. Searching key terms using techniques such as phrasing, wildcards and Boolean operators⁴.
5. Cross-validating sources.

In Milestone 10, four Technology Areas were identified and presented. These four Technology Areas comprise: Dynamic control; Positioning; Infrastructure and vehicle connectivity; and Vehicle automation. Enforcement options and building blocks presented in Milestone 10 are conceptualised in a broader sense here, that is, not just applied for enforcement purposes. With this deliverable, we decomposed the Technology Areas into the smallest units possible i.e. each individual type of technology. This facilitated a more accurate assessment of market penetration, and potential effects on the transport system and society more broadly.

The implementation of such technologies has advanced at a faster rate in some contexts e.g. in the United Kingdom, the Netherlands and the Nordic countries than in others. As such, we detailed the advancements in these contexts to a greater extent in this report. We developed a framework as a means of classifying the respective technologies. This framework is presented in Table 1 in the Findings section.

We then examined the cross-cutting aspects that affect the diffusion and adaptation of these technologies and how they do this. The cross-cutting aspects of most relevance in this instance are **Governance and Financing** and **User Needs and Public Acceptance**, following the ReVeAL framework⁵. The ways in which policies shape the development and execution of UVARs, and how business models can be

² Cases where concrete existing applications or tests exist, or are deemed to be within reach in the near future.

³ See [ReVeAL webpage - Resources overview - Publications](#)

⁴ See [Search techniques - Search methods & techniques - LibGuides at Erasmus University Rotterdam \(eur.nl\)](#) for an overview.

⁵ See [Transition Areas » Civitas ReVeAL \(civitas-reveal.eu\)](#) for more information on the cross-cutting aspects in the ReVeAL framework (which at an earlier stage in the project were referred to as “transition areas”).

developed in tandem with these policies were studied, with potential impacts on transport systems and society more broadly then discussed.

We strived to reduce the risk of missing some developments by consulting with key actors in areas that are less prominent or outspoken. Although we have strived to reduce this risk, we cannot exclude the possibility that we have missed some developments, particularly in cases where accounts may only exist in languages other than the ones in which our key terms feature (i.e., English, Swedish, Norwegian and Danish)⁶.

⁶ Having spoken to several relevant actors we have learned that other key work of importance for informing this report is not yet complete and could contain information of crucial relevance, but our project timing did not allow us to wait for its publication.

Findings

Having gathered material from the various sources detailed in the Methods section and having drawn on the previous work from the ReVeAL project, we drew up the **UVAR future options technology framework**, presented in Table 1. This framework classifies the types of technologies according to the role they play in the development and execution of UVARs. This framework also comprises four roles: **Facilitators**; **Influencers**; **Enhancers**; and **Contributors**. There are several interdependencies between the roles and technologies.

- **Facilitators** comprise technologies *in vehicles and infrastructure* that can affect the UVAR landscape in that they can create both the opportunity to develop UVARs and the necessity to execute new UVARs.
- **Influencers** comprise digital technologies *more broadly* that can affect the implementation and possibilities to develop new UVARs.
- **Enhancers** are conceptualised as tools that are not linked to a specific technology that bring with them new opportunities to support, steer and monitor compliance and allow for new ways of managing existing UVARs and implementing new UVARs, and are complemented by information to and from users.
- **Contributors** constitute more specific measures for governance and monitoring that can contribute to the effectiveness, implementation and support of and need for UVARs, complemented by information to and from users.

Table 1 UVAR future options technology framework

Technology roles	Technologies
Facilitators	Connected vehicles and infrastructure
	Autonomous vehicles
Influencers	Cameras with automatic recognition
	Positioning and/or connectivity technologies (GNSS; RFID; DSRC; 2G/3G/4G/5G; Bluetooth)
Enhancers	Geofencing
	Advanced Driver Assistance Systems
Contributors	Dynamic management / traffic signalling / ITS / rerouting
	Dynamic kerbside management
	Data coordination / shared data platforms for monitoring and analysing trends

Interdependencies between technology roles

The technologies are classified according to the technology role category within which they best fit. However, several technologies could arguably feature in more than one category. Furthermore, there are considerable interactions and interdependencies between the technology roles. For instance, *Connected vehicles and infrastructure* (a Facilitator) and *Positioning and/or connectivity technologies* (an Influencer) are mutually dependent in that they rely on one another to produce a solution for the execution and management of UVARs. This combination of technologies could then indeed be complemented by *Geofencing*, which features in a third technology role category, Enhancers. As such, the technology roles should not be treated as independent of one another. Several UVAR solutions draw on a variety of technology roles.

Facilitators

Facilitators comprise technologies in vehicles and infrastructure that can affect the UVAR landscape in that they can both create the opportunity to develop UVARs and the necessity to execute new UVARs. Here we detail the recent developments concerning Facilitators of key importance, namely *Connected vehicles and infrastructure* and *Autonomous vehicles*.

Connected vehicles and infrastructure

The connection of vehicles to mobile networks is of central importance for the advancement of UVARs. The connection of vehicles to mobile networks began in the beginning of the 1990s, with this connection associated with both open and hidden functions. The user of the vehicle is aware of the former, while only the vehicle manufacturers are aware of and have access to the latter⁷.

Newer vehicles have hidden connection functions with respect to temperature, speed, etc. The data collected on these parameters are received by the manufacturers and are then used for analyses and are also sold for commercial purposes (see footnote 7). Such commercial purposes could include satellite navigation and traffic management services and products.

'E-call' is an open connection function, and most users are aware of it. Of key importance for the advancement of UVARs is the fact that since April 2018 all new vehicles sold within the EU must be equipped with e-call functions. This means that, for instance, the vehicle's sensors detect when the airbag is released. The vehicle itself then alerts the emergency services, sending data on the vehicle's position (see footnote 7).

The fact that all new cars are connected brings with it opportunities such as the example described above where emergency services are automatically alerted in the event of a crash. However, how this can be linked to goals pertaining to environmental and social sustainability is unclear. Data regulations may inhibit possibilities to use this technology for UVARs owing to e.g. restrictions for third-party use. This is despite the apparent relevance of this technology for UVAR advancement. Further studies are required in order to indicate if, how and under which circumstances this technology and data could be used for UVAR purposes.

Autonomous vehicles

In the last decade or so, huge investments in autonomous vehicle technologies have been made. This is despite high levels of uncertainty surrounding both their political and societal acceptance and their safety claims⁸. Currently, there is still a relatively high level of uncertainty surrounding the need for autonomous vehicles. However, UVARs designed in certain ways could draw on the technology. Similarly, UVARs, if designed in certain ways, could generate the need for autonomous vehicles in some contexts, in keeping

⁷ See https://www.trafa.se/globalassets/rapporter/2019/rapport-2019_8-uppkopplade-samverkande-och-automatiserade-fordon-farkoster-och-system---ett-kunskapsunderlag.pdf

⁸ See <https://www.washingtonpost.com/outlook/2022/02/04/self-driving-cars-why/>

with our conceptualisation of the technology as a Facilitator (i.e. creating both the opportunity to develop UVARs and the necessity to execute new UVARs).

In recent years, key actors in the field of autonomous vehicles such as Google/Waymo and Volvo have contributed to considerable developments in this mobility product/service area. To date, applications of autonomous vehicle technologies have mainly been found in trucks and private cars. However, applications have also been found in the mobility service sector, encompassing taxi and public transport (bus) services. Google's Self-Driving Car, Waymo, became its own independent company in 2016 and has provided public taxi transport services since 2017. Since then, the service has developed to provide services by entirely autonomous – driverless – taxi vehicles. These are, however, limited to certain circumstances and geographical areas. This limitation is enforced through the use of geofencing⁹ (a technology we have categorised as an Enhancer).

Similarly, Volvo Cars intends to introduce its unsupervised autonomous driving feature in the state of California during 2022¹⁰. If the scheme is deemed safe on highways, the company plans to include this as an optional add-on to a forthcoming electric vehicle. The company is currently testing the technology's functionalities. The company claims the regulatory framework in California facilitates the introduction of autonomous driving (to a greater extent than elsewhere). The autonomous vehicle technology adopted by the company involves a combination of a LiDAR sensor, five radars, eight cameras and sixteen ultrasonic sensors with continual, 'over-the-air' software rollouts (see footnote 10).

Regulatory frameworks, and differences in the way they are interpreted, can affect the rate at which autonomous vehicles (and other technologies) are adopted, and for UVARs in particular. While Volvo claims that the regulatory framework in California facilitates the introduction of autonomous driving, this is not necessarily the case elsewhere. The conditions for the introduction of autonomous vehicles in Israel, for instance, are regarded as rather unique. The country has adopted a centralised approach to the testing and regulation of autonomous vehicles, which can be said to have both advantages and disadvantages. An advantage is that its centralised, systematic and concentrated approach is considered to foster flexibility. A disadvantage is that application processes can be slow and can hinder developments in the realm of autonomous vehicles. The regulatory framework has been described by some as quite demanding, which is argued to lead to heightened levels of uncertainty¹¹.

The project *Bridging gaps for the adoption of automated vehicles* (BRAVE) detail their findings on the acceptance of conditionally automated cars (CACs)¹², drawing on a survey of respondents in the general population. They detail that there was an overall positive attitude towards CACs among respondents. Respondents indicated that they anticipate a positive effect on traffic safety. However, respondents appeared to be somewhat reluctant with respect to their own personal intention to use CACs. Women's responses were associated with a lower level of general acceptance than those of men. Older

⁹ See <https://waymo.com/waymo-one/>

¹⁰ See <https://www.media.volvocars.com/global/en-gb/media/pressreleases/292917/volvo-cars-unsupervised-autonomous-driving-feature-ride-pilot-to-debut-in-california>

¹¹ See [The path to autonomous vehicles in Israel - comment - The Jerusalem Post \(jpost.com\)](#).

¹² See [Microsoft Word - BRAVE D2.3_final.docx \(brave-project.eu\)](#)

respondents' responses were also linked to lower levels of acceptance than those of younger ones. Trends in responses differed across countries and types of transport mode use.

Several recent studies have examined the (potential) introduction of autonomous vehicles in different contexts. One study found that of the 120 largest cities in the US, most have begun to plan for autonomous vehicles, with larger and faster-growing cities being more prepared than others¹³. Having surveyed officials in these cities, the study found that most were optimistic but that approximately one-third were concerned about effects for sustainability, with some concerned that the wider use of autonomous vehicles could mean increases in vehicle kilometres travelled. The study concluded that cities could facilitate the advancement of the introduction of autonomous vehicles through cooperation with one another and through tacit learning processes. This cooperation and tacit learning would assist in developing more coherent strategies and developing a common understanding of best practices (see footnote 13).

In another study on the same topic,¹⁴ it was found that, broadly speaking, officials expressed strong personal support for the introduction of autonomous vehicles but that they were concerned about the bureaucratic and legal capacity of cities to intervene beyond certain specific areas (beyond e.g. regulations concerning land use, equity, right-of-way, pedestrian space, etc.). Respondents were also doubtful of political support for policies facilitating the wider use of autonomous vehicles, with a minority of respondents stating that they expect to see political support for such a policy.

A third study examined the perceptions of autonomous vehicle safety across almost 42,000 participants in 51 different countries¹⁵. This study found that young, highly educated men in employment and with higher incomes were the most optimistic about the safety of autonomous vehicles. They also found that people in Western European countries were largely aware of the existence of the technology but that there was a palpable pessimism towards the safety of autonomous vehicles among this group. People in developing countries in Asia were the most optimistic among respondents. The authors frame the introduction of autonomous vehicles as an opportunity to overcome the disparity in traffic safety that exists between different parts of the world.

A further study sought to give an insight into how the introduction of autonomous vehicles would affect different population groups, suggesting that its introduction in public transport vehicles could provide an equity benefit, provided this was for higher occupancy vehicles (see reference below for more details on this reasoning)¹⁶. A more recent study found that equity concerns seem to be inherent in the implementation of autonomous vehicles, with officials reasoning along equity dimensions and engaging equity arguments when dealing with their implementation¹⁷.

¹³ See Freeman et al. 2019: [Are Cities Prepared for Autonomous Vehicles? Planning for Technological Change by U.S. Local Governments \(trb.org\)](#)

¹⁴ See Freeman et al. 2020: [Urban Science | Free Full-Text | Policies for Autonomy: How American Cities Envision Regulating Automated Vehicles \(mdpi.com\)](#)

¹⁵ See Moody et al. 2019: [Public perceptions of autonomous vehicle safety: An international comparison - ScienceDirect](#)

¹⁶ See Cohn et al. 2019: [Examining the Equity Impacts of Autonomous Vehicles: A Travel Demand Model Approach - Jesse Cohn, Richard Ezike, Jeremy Martin, Kwasi Donkor, Matthew Ridgway, Melissa Balding, 2019 \(sagepub.com\)](#)

¹⁷ See Soh and Martens 2022: [Value dimensions of autonomous vehicle implementation through the Ethical Delphi - ScienceDirect](#)

The findings from these studies indicate that the landscape for the introduction of autonomous vehicles is still very uncertain and that the support of politicians and the general public alike is not clear-cut. Cities – larger cities in particular – appear to be planning for the introduction of autonomous vehicles but the mechanisms for doing so appear unclear. The general public appears to be sceptical about the safety of this technology. These trends indicate that, despite investments by large companies, we have yet to see the direction this technology and its diffusion will take, and indeed what this will mean for the advancement of UVARs, both existing and new.

Influencers

Influencers comprise digital technologies more broadly that can affect implementation and possibilities to develop new UVARs. In this section, we examine the recent developments with respect to one of the Influencers of key importance, *Positioning and/or connectivity technologies*.

Positioning and/or connectivity technologies

Positioning and/or connectivity technologies include but are not limited to GNSS, RFID, DSRC, 2G/3G/4G/5G and Bluetooth technologies. Findings from the Nordic Way 2 project indicate that, in general, cellular network connectivity (usually in the form of cellular data) is the most commonly used type of connectivity technology. One example of a new application of relevance for UVAR-advancement is traffic light monitoring. This solution has so far been developed using an exchange of information between vehicles (occupants), and between the vehicle and the cloud through cellular network connectivity. This, in turn, informs the driver waiting at or approaching a red light about the status of the signal (whether and when the light will turn green, red, etc.).¹⁸

Another pilot carried out as part of the Nordic Way 2 project has developed the time to green concept through a human-machine interface. This technology allows for the driver to anticipate how many seconds remain before the signal will turn green, with the intention of making driving more efficient¹⁹. It is further argued that 5G technology allows for the necessary latency and bandwidth for these solutions to be further developed. This is compared to the solutions available today (see footnote 18).

Similarly, Ericsson and Scania in their vehicle-to-vehicle solutions have drawn on 5G and LTE (radio waves/electromagnetic radiation) to improve efficiency among platoons of trucks so that they can drive together in close proximity and, as such, improve efficiency. It is argued that this reduces the carbon footprint of these vehicles²⁰.

¹⁸See https://uploads-ssl.webflow.com/5c487d8f7febe4125879c2d8/5fe31251770a09c2b1b33b96_NW2_A9_%20Final%20report_ver1.0.pdf

¹⁹See https://uploads-ssl.webflow.com/5c487d8f7febe4125879c2d8/5ffc6b31ed110e3811332b20_NW2_A5_%20Final%20report%20Norwegian%20Pilots_ver1.1.pdf

²⁰ See <https://www.ericsson.com/en/cases/2017/scania-and-ericsson-vehicle-to-vehicle-communication>

These positioning and/or connectivity technologies bring with them considerable potential for the advancement of existing UVARs as well as the execution of new ones. For instance, the range and scope of UVARs could potentially increase as a result of said technologies. These technologies combined with geofencing could mean a significant opportunity for UVARs. These technologies are however still in their early stages, and have yet to see diffusion or market penetration in a wider context. These technologies are also likely to be a cause of concern for city officials, politicians and the general public for the same reasons as autonomous vehicles have been found to be a cause for concern (acceptance, capacity and safety concerns, etc.), outlined in an earlier section of this report. Traffic safety concerns in broader contexts have yet to be examined in detail. This will be crucial for market penetration of these technologies.

Enhancers

Enhancers are conceptualised as tools that are not linked to a specific technology that bring with them new opportunities to support, steer and monitor compliance and allow for new ways of managing existing UVARs and implementing new UVARs, and are complemented by information to and from users.

Geofencing

Geofencing is a conceptual tool consisting of an array of possible applications. The ReVeAL project²¹ and Horizon 2020 EU project GeoSense²² have previously defined the concepts of “geofence” and “geofencing”, respectively (see footnotes 21 and 22 for definitions). The main characteristic of an application is whether it is established based on a regulation or on a contract, and if the conditions and regulations are supposed to be static or dynamic (see Figure 1). The understanding of these characteristics can be distorted by the fact that a contract-based application can relate to an existing traffic regulation stating that an actor agrees to guarantee their compliance through the application. An application is supposedly less difficult to implement if it is static and based on a contract or an agreement between a limited number of stakeholders. The complexity increases when regulations are involved, penalties/fines are associated with it, and/or if it is supposed to be dynamic or smart.

²¹ In the Geofencing Guidance note (Sadler, 2021) the ReVeAL-project defines a geofence as “a virtual perimeter around a real-world geographic area. The perimeter can have predefined boundaries such as a school zone or a neighbourhood, or it can be dynamically generated, such as a radius around a point, or a perimeter that changes”.

²² The Horizon 2020 EU project GeoSense define geofencing (working definition) as the “creation of a geofence for monitoring, informing, and controlling traffic (mobile objects/vehicles) located within, entering or exiting the geofence, using electronic communication technologies or pre-defined geofences embedded into the mobile objects/vehicles, where a geofence is defined as a virtual geographically located boundary, statically or dynamically defined” (Hansen, et al., 2021).

Figure 1 Main characteristics of a geofencing application

The interest in geofencing compared to other options for ensuring compliance assumes that the applications either:

1. Bring a more efficient method for raising the level of compliance with existing regulations
2. Enable new regulations which are either
 - a. More precise, or
 - b. More general.

In theory, geofencing brings with it the possibility of functionally complete coverage in both time and space, by which it could potentially guarantee specific behaviours and by that eliminate traffic violations such as speeding or unwanted route choices.

By this date (May 2022), the potential impact of different geofencing applications is still uncertain. The GeoSense project²³ has gathered documentation from six pilot projects with different applications that all claim a positive societal effect. When studying the project's results, the positive societal effect is, however, in most cases not clear. For some of them, the causal relationship between the effects and the specific geofencing application is questionable. For others, the effects are small or have not (yet) been scientifically verified. The existing data on effects and potential impacts from studying pilot projects on geofencing applications is limited²⁴.

The Swedish research and innovation program on geofencing led by CLOSER²⁵ has released two recent reports that are relevant for assessing market penetration, business models, potential societal benefits as well as challenges and needs. The first report²⁶ is an analysis of the commercial market for geofencing services for road transport applications for the coming 5-10 years (limited to end customers). One of the conclusions is that geofencing is becoming more common, especially for fleet management. Applications for other uses, such as controlling speed and propulsion, are still being developed and are hence less mature. The report claims that a growing general awareness regarding traffic safety and emissions will support the deployment of new services. The market analysis also concludes that service providers do not see technical development as a challenge. They emphasise that the technology and data exist but a lack of demand hinders them from deploying these services on the market.

This lack of demand most likely reflects the uncertainty in the actual benefits for different stakeholders. In the second report, CLOSER assessed different stakeholder needs regarding geofencing in the road transport system²⁷. The interviewees consist of different stakeholders representing for example relevant

²³ See Hansen et al. (2021): Current state of the art and use case description on geofencing for traffic management <https://closer.lindholmen.se/sites/default/files/2021-11/report-on-current-state-of-the-art-and-use-case-description-on-geofencing-for-traffic-management.pdf>

²⁴ See Solér et al (2022): Geofencing - att uppskatta effekter, potential och genomslagstakt https://closer.lindholmen.se/sites/default/files/2022-05/geofencing_effekt_potential_genomslagstakt_2022-1.pdf

²⁵ A collaboration and innovation platform for sustainable transport gathering cities, public agencies and bodies, and different market actors in Sweden. CLOSER is also a ReVeAL Reference Group member.

²⁶ CLOSER (2021): Report on market analysis – geofencing-based services in road transport https://closer.lindholmen.se/sites/default/files/2021-11/report_on_market_analysis_-_geofencing-based_services_in_road_transport_.pdf

²⁷ CLOSER (2022): Assessment of stakeholder needs regarding geofencing in the transport system <https://closer.lindholmen.se/sites/default/files/2022-05/assessment-of-stakeholder-needs-regarding-geofencing-in-the-transport-system.pdf>

authorities, public transport actors, freight transport actors, taxi/car and bike sharing and rental actors, ports and terminals, construction companies and insurance companies. One piece of information from a commercial transport service provider detailed in the report is that any additional cost must generate a direct economic benefit. A problem here could be the fact that the wider benefits of an application do not often match the costs for the stakeholder who is expected to invest in a technology and/or service. The respondents suggested potential benefits from geofencing applications which then were divided into three main categories: access control, speed restrictions and informational geofencing.

Access control zone applications forcing (or controlling) Plug-in Hybrid Electric Vehicles (PHEVs) into electric mode are mentioned in both CLOSER reports and in the GeoSense report above. Within the ReVeAL-project, Transport for London however recently decided not to trial this application together with City of London in their work towards introducing Zero Emission Zones²⁸. The main justification for not doing this is the fact that the deployment of Battery Electric Vehicles (BEVs) in favour of PHEVs is possibly sooner than previously expected. And with this forecast in mind, the investment needed for controlling PHEVs is thought to be “a very expensive way to control just one mode”.

Projected Londonwide car vkm proportions

²⁸ Transport for London (2022): Geofencing note v 2.

Figure 2 Graph showing the latest forecast of BEV uptake versus decline in Internal Combustion Engine (ICE) cars in London (Transport for London, 2022)

The forecast from London is part of a wider trend in Europe where BEVs are expected to reach upfront cost price parity with Internal Combustion Engines (ICEs) by 2025-2027²⁹.

That emission zone applications (such as access control zone applications) force PHEVs into electric mode is problematic for cost efficiency. This is because behavioural patterns with PHEVs by default support electric mode operation in cities³⁰. This means that from the start PHEVs already run most of the time on electricity in cities. There are also voices raising concern about the risk of zero-emission zones with geofencing applications potentially increasing emissions if drivers need to charge their batteries using the combustion engine before entering a zone³¹. An interesting note from TfL's decision is that they chose to step away from their trial even though they have much of the infrastructure and processes needed for a large-scale implementation in place (see footnote 28).

One possible conclusion is that emission zone applications could be made more cost-effective in the near future (5-10 years) with a small-scale solution based on contracts or voluntary agreements.

Advanced Driver Assistance Systems

Advanced Driver Assistance Systems (ADAS) is a collective name for multiple different technologies and/or functions. The purpose of ADAS is to support the driver and/or the vehicle with information to make driving safer, more comfortable and/or more efficient³² (Himabindu & Yasmeen, 2014).

The distinction between ADAS and geofencing is not always clear. For instance, an Intelligent Speed Assistance (ISA)-system may rely on electronic cartographical data as an input method, together with other input method(s) (EU, 2021). One general difference could be that ADAS has developed from an individual (support-function) perspective, whereas geofencing in road transport has a more collective and controlling perspective.

Most of the UVAR-relevant technology in the existing vehicle fleet is there thanks to ADAS. The EU regulation requiring ISA to be fitted in new vehicles from May 2022³³ (EU, 2021) could, depending on what input methods and control functions vehicle manufacturers choose, mean a more rapid deployment of these technologies. The main challenge remaining regarding technologies is then the fact that vehicle manufacturers are reluctant to provide access to in-vehicle data and, in particular, for third-party solutions³⁴.

²⁹See BloombergNEF (2021)_ https://www.transportenvironment.org/wp-content/uploads/2021/08/2021_05_05_Electric_vehicle_price_parity_and_adoption_in_Europe_Final.pdf

³⁰ Arnesen et al. (2021): Geofencing to Enable Differentiated Road User Charging, Transportation Research Record, 0361198121995510.

³¹ Transport & Environment (2020): Plug-in hybrids: Is Europe heading for a new dieselgate?

³² Himabindu & Yasmeen (2014): Driver Assistance System - Shared Steering Between Human and Automation, International Journal of Advances in Applied Science and Engineering, 199-202.

³³ European Commission (2021): Official Journal of the European Union - L409 - Volume 64, <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=OJ%3AL%3A2021%3A409%3ATOC>

³⁴ Scholliers et al. (2020): Study on the feasibility, costs and benefits of retrofitting advanced driver assistance to improve road safety, <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/72659808-7ec1-11ea-aea8-01aa75ed71a1>

Contributors

Contributors constitute more specific measures for governance and monitoring that can contribute to the effectiveness, implementation and support of and need for UVARs, complemented by information to and from users.

Dynamic management / traffic signalling / ITS / rerouting

One recent development in the realm of dynamic traffic management is TMaaS (Traffic Management as a Service)³⁵, a project initiated in the city of Ghent where mobility data from a range of different transport modes is collected and harmonised. The intention is to both collect (partly in a crowdsourcing mechanism) and administer a wide range of information (weather information, social media messages, etc.) in real-time, from and to the city's inhabitants. This is in order to tailor individual information and allow inhabitants to access the relevant information to choose available sustainable means of travel. The platform is currently based in Ghent, but the intention is for other cities of similar size to be able to use this platform and to develop the concept elsewhere.

Such a platform is relevant for UVAR advancement (both for existing and for new) in that information can be shared to advise inhabitants in real-time with respect to the regulations to which they need to adhere in the specific UVAR context. Such solutions appear to still be in the pilot phase and have yet to achieve a more expansive market penetration. Nevertheless, there is considerable potential for UVAR advancement. There are, however, several issues concerning data management, validation of sources, etc. that must first be ironed out.

Dynamic kerbside management

The ReVeAL project defines dynamic kerbside management as “...*the management of kerb adjacent space according to the time-varying need and demand of different uses or users*”. The purpose of dynamic kerbside management is the “...move away from long-time storage for private vehicles and the allocation of space to other functions”³⁶ (Solér, Kerrén, & Lindgren, 2020).

Mobility products and services regarding dynamic kerbside management consist of different tools and technology for data collection and management, traffic order management, stakeholder engagement, and enforcement. Since the publication of the ReVeAL-deliverable 3.8 “*Barriers to dynamic kerbside management*”(see footnote 36), the main area of development has been within the standardisation of data, communication, and procedures. Examples in this regard are the EU's project UvarBox³⁷ and the UK Department for Transport's project for adopting a digital model for traffic regulation orders³⁸. For instance, with a digital model, all information should be standardised with clear definitions and the format should be machine-readable. The challenges regarding digitalisation are shared with all other technology roles and are not specific to dynamic kerbside management. The main challenge within dynamic kerbside

³⁵ See [TMaaS - Traffic Management as a Service \(Closed\) | UIA - Urban Innovative Actions \(uia-initiative.eu\)](#) for more information.

³⁶ Solér et al. (2020): Barriers to dynamic curbside management.

³⁷ See [About UVAR Box](#) for more information

³⁸ See [TRO Data Model Alpha Report](#) for more information

management is, apart from technological and digital aspects, the need to shift space allocation to meet wider public goals and to secure equitable access distribution³⁹.

Data coordination / shared data platforms for monitoring and analysing trends

Data coordination and shared data platforms can assist in informing UVARs and can contribute to the management and steering of UVARs in different ways. One example of a mobility data platform is Vianova, which works in a similar way to the TMaaS solution but is perhaps more passive. This platform instead uses data from connected vehicles and mobility devices to assist in the control and management of, for instance, where devices are parked and during which timeframes⁴⁰. The platform is also designed to assist with planning and to assist in regulation and compliance, and to assist in pricing strategies.

Discussion

As with most innovations and new technologies, the **governance and institutional conditions** required to facilitate their introduction are likely to lag behind the actual technological advancements. In the case of UVARs, the institutional requirements may be in place to facilitate the UVAR itself but not the desired technology. This is particularly relevant with respect to data collection, management, storage and use. This could potentially present problems for using new technology in UVARs⁴¹. It could be argued that the wider an application is, the more difficult it is to implement it, with respect to legislation, data integrity and system requirements.

A wider demand for a technology is often generated through legislation and/or regulation. Some cities lack awareness of the introduction of relevant legislation and/or regulation and need to be made aware of such changes (see footnote 41). The relevant technologies appear to exist and are “ready” but legislation and/or regulation are needed to generate a need for a relevant application of the technology. The institutional framework and conditions required often lag behind the generation of such a need, even if using the technology is desired.

There appears to be a mutually dependent relationship between market forces, technological advancements and the **financial conditions required for the introduction of technologies for the purposes of UVARs**. The city’s scope for action can be somewhat limited depending on the resources and budget available. Cities often lack the budget and resources needed to make such dramatic changes and are also hesitant to facilitate the interests of private actors such as vehicle manufacturers and logistics companies. As such, the management of transitions can be challenging. For the city, defining its and others’ roles can also be difficult⁴². Determining which technology to use and the ways in which it

³⁹ Marsden et al. (2020) Parking futures: Curbside management in the era of 'new mobility' services in British and Australian cities. Land Use Policy, volume 91.

⁴⁰ See [Vianova | Mobility Data Platform for Cities & Transport Providers](#)

⁴¹ Interview with Expert A, 20 May 2022.

⁴² Interview Expert B, 15 October 2020.

should be used for UVARs can also be a significant challenge and can have far-reaching consequences far into the future.

Pooling resources and coordinating approaches between cities could function as a potential means of overcoming such challenges. Furthermore, establishing a common understanding of the technologies available and how to facilitate them could prove to be crucial. In this sense, agreeing on definitions with a high degree of precision for what exactly is meant when referring to the different technologies is an important step towards facilitation.

However, there are considerable overlaps and interdependencies between different technologies, as outlined above. Some technologies appear to become somewhat redundant in tandem with other developments, e.g., electrification. As such, one transition linked to a specific innovation has the potential to make another redundant. Problems such as lock-in situations can also present themselves. Such problems can be overcome by requiring open standards and protocols as part of procurement processes.

The introduction of technologies for UVARs is also dependent on user needs, as well as political and public acceptance more broadly. In this sense, it is important to consider exactly which groups will be affected and the ways in which they will be (differently) affected by the introduction of the respective technologies. The digital divide and differences in digital literacy among groups could mean that some could be put at risk of social exclusion as a result of the introduction of some technologies. Not everyone has access to a smartphone, and not everyone has the digital literacy to download and use the various apps often required to avail of the regulations and information described in this report. This could result in some groups avoiding some parts of cities or some activities in order to reduce the risk of unintentionally not complying with regulations. When there is an unequal availability of information, the digitalisation of some processes could result in an even larger digital divide. However, the digital divide differs from context to context. In Sweden, a large majority of the population has a smartphone, and the minority who do not is likely to be concentrated in certain social groups (e.g. people with lower incomes and older people). While in Belgium, for instance, the majority with access to a smartphone is much smaller.

Furthermore, it is important to examine and follow up on how the effects of UVAR advancement are distributed among groups in society. If this distribution is not examined, we run the risk of an even more inequitable distribution of transport system effects.

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